

Analysis of the Use of E-Learning as a Historical Learning Medium during the Covid-19 Pandemic

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ABSTRACT: The purpose of this study was to see how E-learning applications were used in history lectures during the Covid-19 period. This research uses descriptive-evaluative research strategy with Mixed Methods technique (quantitative and qualitative). The descriptive-evaluative analysis in this study is limited to the E-Learning program as a historical learning medium. The subjects of this study were teachers of history subjects and students at SMA Negeri 1 Kota Padang who used E-Learning. Data was collected through interviews, documentation, and distributing questionnaires. This study uses descriptive statistical analysis, namely calculating the amount of data obtained from questionnaire data and then evaluating the data in the form of percentages. The influence of online learning with E-Learning applications on students' historical thinking skills and historical awareness abilities is substantial. Furthermore, using E-Learning technology into history lessons may aid students in developing a stronger sense of national identity. As a result, it is possible to infer that the E-learning application had a significant impact on history learning during the COVID-19 epidemic.

KEYWORDS: Covid-19, E-learning, Historical Learning

INTRODUCTION

COVID-19 is a highly contagious disease caused by the severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2). It started in Wuhan, China, and has now spread across the continent (Bchetnia et al., 2020). It is mainly spread between individuals during close contact, resulting in millions of deaths. As one of the preventive measures against the spread of the coronavirus infection, which resulted in the paralysis of global activities, a lockdown and social distance were imposed. With the implementation of social distance, there are significant changes in people's lives (Nadikattu et al., 2020). Technology plays an important role in new life during the implementation of social distancing (Nguyen et al., 2020). Likewise, in terms of learning, there is a shift in the learning process from traditional to electronic learning, especially in the school system, which is completely closed and must be continued with the academic curriculum.

In order to combat the COVID-19 epidemic, the Minister of Education has directed that online classrooms be used. Teachers were expected to handle the teaching and learning process via online classrooms. Students were not permitted to attend school to participate in class activities, but they were required to study at home. To study and understand the materials and assignments assigned by their teacher, the pupils had to access the internet. To address the issues, school stakeholders must develop a new management structure for supporting the educational system. They must draft a new regulation governing the use of the school-at-home and work-at-home systems.

Online learning is a type of learning that takes place via the internet and eliminates the need for teachers and students to interact face-to-face throughout the learning process (Stoetzel & Shedrow 2020). Online learning may be done on a variety of internet-connected electronic devices, including laptops, tablets, and smartphones (Castillo-Manzano et al., 2017). However, gadgets cannot be used directly in online learning since it necessitates the usage of supporting software such as E-Learning, Google Classroom, Edmodo, Zenius, Microsoft Team, and others (Hermanto & Srimulyani, 2021). During the epidemic, practically all schools and institutions in Indonesia embraced e-learning as one of the ways to deal with distance learning. E-Learning is learning that occurs when internet technology is utilized to support, provide, and allow remote learning activities (Logan, Johnson, & Worsham, 2021). E-learning may be accessed at any time and can distribute and provide teaching-learning resources in a variety of forms, including presentations, audios, videos, PDFs, e-mails, and word documents.

History is one of the subjects that students are taught from elementary school through high school and into college. History is a topic that differs from other subjects in terms of study characteristics. History learning can only be traced through existing historical sources because the target of study focuses on previous occurrences. On the other hand, the goal of history education is to develop historical knowledge, a sense of nationalism, historical thinking, and excellent character in pupils. So, how role does E-learning play in accomplishing the goals of studying history, given the nature of learning that differs from that of other subjects? As a result, the purpose of this article is to examine the usage of E-Learning in learning during the COVID-19 epidemic.

METHODOLOGY

In this study, the technique of Mixed Methods (quantitative and qualitative) was used with a descriptive-evaluative research approach. In this study, the descriptive-evaluative analysis is limited to the E-Learning program which is used as a historical learning medium. The subjects of this study were teachers of history subjects and students at SMA Negeri 1 Kota Padang who used E-Learning. Interviews, documentation, and the distribution of questionnaires were used to collect data. Interviews with students and teachers were done to understand more about the historical learning process that was carried out using an online system. The documentation is based on the E-Learning media that was utilized. The purpose of the questionnaire is to gather information on student and teacher reactions to the use of E-Learning in history classes. The data analysis technique employed in this study is descriptive statistical analysis, which entails determining the quantity of data collected from questionnaire data and then analyzing the data in percentage form. The calculation pattern is based on the Sugiyono pattern (2012):

$$PS = \frac{ST}{SM} \times 100\%$$

Description:

PS = Score percentage

ST = Total score generated

SM = The highest possible score that should be earned

The data collected is divided into four categories:

Table 1. Category of evaluation

Category	Percentage
Very Good	86-100%
Good	70-85%
Enough	50-69%
Not Good	1-49%

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Description of data

1. Teachers and students' readiness to participate in online learning

Teachers and students must be properly prepared to participate in this remote learning process for online learning to be successful. This is because preparation has a significant impact on the effectiveness of online learning implementation in meeting the learning objectives that have been specified. The graphic below depicts teacher preparedness in dealing with online learning. The analyses' findings are depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Teachers and students' readiness to participate in online learning

Figure 1 shows that the majority of history teachers at SMA Negeri 1 Kota Padang are prepared to teach utilizing the online method (60 %). Similarly, the majority of students responded that they were willing to participate in online learning. Even 25% of students said they were very prepared to confront the learning process when it transitioned from face-to-face to online. The readiness of teachers and students to take part in online learning will have a positive effect on their interactions in the learning process and the learning outcomes achieved (Kaymak & Horzum, 2013). Online learning readiness refers to the independent preparation of teachers and students to utilize various forms of technology, such as the internet and, in particular, computer-mediated communication tools in online learning (Zou et al., 2021). Readiness to learn online also refers to how teachers and students manage their time, as well as how they control and regulate themselves in order to stay engaged in the learning process (Rapanta et al., 2020). Based on the information presented above, it is obvious that both teachers and students are ready to be involved in online learning. Employing technology in education to promote historical understanding and the development of historical thinking skills (Seixas, 2017) can help to improve learning, transform teaching techniques, and increase student engagement.

2. Perceptions of the usage of E-Learning applications in history lessons by teachers and students

Teachers' and students' perceptions of the use of E-Learning applications in history learning can be assessed using three criteria: the ease with which teachers and students use E-Learning applications, the attractiveness of the E-Learning display in presenting learning in an online format, and the impact of E-Learning on increasing student learning motivation. The three criteria are provided one by one as follows:

a. Operational simplicity

Figure 2. Study findings on the views of teachers and students on the ease of use of E-Learning

Figure 2 shows that the majority of teachers (40 %) said the E-Learning program was easy to use. However, 20% of respondents said that using E-Learning programs was difficult. In terms of students, the majority of students (55 %) said that using the E-

Learning program was easy, while just 10% said it was hard. As a result, it was established that during the Covid-19 epidemic, both teachers and students could readily use the E-Learning application to help the online learning process. This data backs up Eze et al. (2018), which found that teachers and students prefer to utilize E-learning as a distance learning medium because of its simplicity of use and operation. Discussion forums, notification messages, content coverage, and other features that allow students to share ideas, connect, and get suggestions are made more practical and useful, such as one-click and attractive to use.

b. Interesting E-Learning Display

Figure 3. The findings of a study on teacher and student perceptions of the E-Learning application's attractiveness

According to figure 3, 60% of teachers found the E-Studying application to be engaging as a medium for learning history in the context of distant learning. This application piqued the interest of 40% of teachers as well. Similarly, 62.5 % said the E-Learning program was extremely fascinating as a historical learning medium. This suggests that both professors and students are enthusiastic about the use of E-Learning applications in remote learning. The findings of this study support those of Syafei et al. (2020), who claim that the E-learning application is one of the online learning media with an appealing look for teachers and students to utilize. Each section will have its own guide, which will be published on the e-learning website and may be downloaded immediately as students have e-learning access. All learning processes are regulated in an integrated manner in e-learning generated through the learning participant account.

c. E-learning has the potential to boost learning motivation.

Figure 4. The findings of a study of teacher and student perspectives on the usefulness of E-Learning apps in improving students' motivation to learn

According to Figure 4, the teacher indicated that the pupils were really enthusiastic about studying with the E-Learning program. In terms of students, the majority of students (45%) said they were inspired to study because of the E-Learning application, and 37.5 % said they were extremely driven to learn because of the E-Learning program. As a result of the facts shown above, it can be stated that the E-Learning program has a significant impact on students' motivation to learn history. The findings of this study corroborate those of Satyawan et al. (2001), who found that 77 % of students' motivation improves when they are given more responsibility. Students' high levels of focus, comprehension, and motivation for online learning using E-Learning result in excellent student

learning results. Conditions and engaging learning material can influence students' concentration while they are studying (Erwiza, Kartiko, & Gimin, 2019). Students may choose and establish a comfortable and conducive learning environment based on their individual needs while they learn online. Students will struggle to concentrate due to the numerous objects in view that may divert their attention. Furthermore, learning with e-learning is something that students are still unfamiliar with, so e-learning is able to draw students' attention to the learning process.

3. The impact of e-learning on achieving historical learning objectives

E-Learning has an impact on the attainment of history learning objectives in general, as shown by historical thinking abilities, historical awareness, and a sense of patriotism. The three aspects are described one by one as follows:

a. E-learning's impact on historical thinking abilities

Figure 5. The findings of an analysis into the impact of e-learning on students' historical thinking skills

The findings of the analysis of the impact of E-Learning on the historical thinking abilities of SMA Negeri 1 Kota Padang students are shown in Figure 5. Figure 5 shows that learning history using an E-Learning application has a 37.5 % impact on students' historical thinking abilities. However, 20% of students said that using the E-Learning program had no effect on their historical thinking skills, while 25% said it had a little impact. Meanwhile, 17.5 % said that using E-Learning programs had a significant impact on their historical thinking skills. This research supports the findings of van Boxtel and Drie (2018), who found that integrating technological media and historical materials in history classes can help students understand about the past. The use of digital learning can promote student involvement in the construction of historical meaning (Malahito & Quimbo, 2020). Using digital media allows students and teachers to increase their digital literacy while also developing historical thinking and comprehension skills (Miguel-Revilla et al., 2020; Oliver & Purichia, 2018).

b. E-learning's impact on students' historical awareness

Figure 6. The findings of an analysis into the impact of e-learning on historical awareness

Figure 6 depicts the findings of the study on the impact of E-Learning on students' historical understanding at SMA Negeri 1 Padang City. According to the data in figure 6, 40% of history learning via E-Learning apps influences students' historical awareness abilities, and 30% of students believe that learning via E-Learning applications has a significant impact on students' historical awareness. However, 17.5 % said that using the E-Learning program had a little impact on their historical awareness abilities, while just 12.5 % said it had no impact. Online education with the digital platforms that are creatively can utilized to provide a space for collaboration and discussion of topics within the History Education. Through online education, history teachers can become more empowered and, if they know how to effectively engage with online education, they will build historical awareness in students (Rasmussen, 2011). They can best prepare themselves by learning how to build historical awareness in students if they are familiar with the features of the relevant software and applications. E-Learning assists teachers and students in generating interactive dialogue in history learning, ensuring that learning stays in the framework of strengthening students' historical awareness through these constrained learning activities.

c. The impact of e-learning on a student's sense of patriotism

Figure 7. The findings of an analysis into the impact of e-learning on students' feeling of nationalism

Figure 7 depicts the findings of the study on the impact of E-Learning on students' feeling of nationalism at SMA Negeri 1 Kota Padang. Figure 7 shows that learning history using an E-Learning application has a 37.5 % impact on students' feeling of nationalism, with 25% of students claiming that learning history through an E-Learning application has a significant impact on their sense of nationalism. However, 17.5 % said that using the E-Learning program had no effect on their nationalism, and 20% said it had a minor impact on their historical knowledge. The use of E-Learning applications in history classes can help students develop a stronger sense of nationalism. The findings of this study back up the findings of Bahrami and Farrokhi (2014), who found that e-learning has a positive impact on strengthening global citizen characteristics like commitment to social justice, critical thinking skills, nationalism, self-esteem, collaboration skills, and respect for cultural diversity by changing people's behavior through planned and purposeful training. The presentation of cultural artifacts in a way that is more realistic, interesting, and accessible to students through video displays gives them a new and interesting experience, which strengthens their sense of national identity and nationalism.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results at SMA Negeri 1 Kota Padang, the majority of history teachers are equipped to teach using the online method. Similarly, the majority of students expressed an interest in participating in online learning. The independent preparation of teachers and students to use various types of technology is referred to as "online learning readiness." The majority of students (45%) claimed the E-Learning program encouraged them to study, and 37.5% said it made them highly motivated to learn. Students' high levels of concentration, understanding, and enthusiasm for online learning through e-learning produce great student learning outcomes. Online learning with E-Learning applications has a significant impact on students' historical thinking skills and historical awareness

abilities. In addition, integrating E-Learning technologies into history lectures might help students develop a stronger sense of nationality. According to the research, studying history through e-learning programs has a significant impact on students' feelings of nationalism and identity.

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